

Assessing the surface electrical conductivity by comparison of X-ray photoelectron spectra under gas and in vacuum environments.

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Abstract

For several decades an open question in many X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) studies was whether or not the results obtained in ultra-high vacuum conditions (UHV) were representative of the sample state in gas atmospheres. As a consequence, near ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) was received by surface scientists as an important tool for in situ characterization of the gas-solid interactions. However, it is not yet clear how, if at all, the surface state formed in contact with the gas is modified when this gas is evacuated. In this work we compare synchrotron-based XPS results recorded at 300 °C on Ni/yttria-stabilized zirconia cermet and $\text{La}_{0.75}\text{Sr}_{0.25}\text{Cr}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ perovskite, under 3.5 mbar O_2 and UHV environments. We found that the surface state formed in O_2 is maintained to a large extent under vacuum. In addition, we demonstrate that the correlation of XPS spectra recorded in the two conditions can provide information regarding the electrical conductivity of the specific surface sites of these complex oxides. Our findings suggest that comparison of XPS measurements in gas and in vacuum environments might be particularly useful in applications where the electronic conductivity at the surface plays a crucial role, as for example in solid oxide electrochemical devices.

1. Introduction

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is a particularly powerful technique for chemical analysis of solid surfaces and nanomaterials [1]. In a typical XPS experiment the sample is maintained under ultra-high vacuum conditions (UHV, $P < 10^{-8}$ mbar), mainly due to the high probability of the emitted photoelectrons to interact with the surrounding medium which causes severe attenuation of the

photoemission signal [2]. UHV is a suitable sample environment in applications where the surface of the solid should be maintained clean of adsorbents, as for example during fabrication and characterization of semiconductor interfaces [3]. However, in many applications, for instance in catalysis or environmental science, solid surfaces are in contact with a reactive medium (gas or liquid) usually in atmospheric pressure and at high temperature. The surface science approach to study gas/solid or liquid/solid interactions, is to form an adsorbed layer of the reactive medium on the solid surface by low pressure exposure ($P < 10^{-5}$ mbar) with the sample at cryogenic temperatures [4]. Nevertheless the significant pressure gap between these experiments and the atmospheric conditions is a major constraint for utilizing the results in real world applications.

An alternative approach, especially developed to study catalytic reactions, is to expose the solid in the reactive medium inside a reactor chamber and subsequently quench the sample and transfer it into the UHV chamber for XPS analysis [5–7]. Despite the fact that this approach gave significant insights about the gas/solid and liquid/solid interactions, uncertainties on the results may arise due to the fact that the surface state may change during transfer to the spectrometer for low-pressure XPS analysis.[8]. In the particular case of solid oxide ion conductors, which are the subject of this paper, the XPS measurements should be preferentially performed at elevated temperatures (around 400 °C). This is because the oxygen ion mobility, as well as the conductivity of the sample, increase at high temperatures thus preventing undesirable electrostatic charging effects induced by the emission of photoelectrons [9]. This requirement raises more concerns about the capacity of oxidized surfaces to withstand the reductive UHV conditions during XPS measurements. Besides, previous studies have reported an influence of the oxygen pressure at the perovskite surface composition [10]. All the above reasons call for a study of the stability of pre-oxidized electrodes in vacuum conditions.

Near ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) has emerged as a powerful technique for *in situ* and *operando* investigations of chemical reactions at pressures of several tenths of mbar [8,11]. The technique is becoming increasingly popular in (electro)catalysis research since it combines high surface sensitivity with chemical specificity and quantitative information, while the sample is under (electro)catalytic operation conditions [12,13]. However, NAP-XPS setups are mainly synchrotron-based and relatively expensive to acquire, which limits broad access to this type of experiments. Therefore, it is interesting to assess if and how much *ex situ* surface analysis of quenched samples (transferred and measured in vacuum) influences the surface characteristics. In this work we compare the surface oxidation state and composition of Ni/YSZ and $\text{La}_{0.75}\text{Sr}_{0.25}\text{Cr}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ under 3.5 mbar O_2 and UHV conditions measured in a synchrotron-based NAP-XPS spectrometer. Interestingly our results show negligible surface modifications of both oxides upon O_2 gas evacuation. More importantly we demonstrate how the comparison of NAP and UHV-XPS

results can provide complementary information about the surface electrical properties of these two oxides commonly used in solid oxide electrochemical devices.

2. Materials and Methods

Commercial NiO-YSZ cermet (Fuel Cell Materials, 66% by weight NiO, 34% by weight YSZ) and laboratory synthesized [14] $\text{La}_{0.75}\text{Sr}_{0.25}\text{Cr}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ perovskites were measured. The two samples were fabricated using a preparation procedure described elsewhere [15]. Near Ambient-Pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) was performed at the NAP-XPS end station of the University Pierre et Marie Curie set on the TEMPO beamline of the SOLEIL synchrotron radiation facility in France. For the measurements, the NiO-YSZ (hereafter Ni/YSZ) and $\text{La}_{0.75}\text{Sr}_{0.25}\text{Cr}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ (hereafter LSCF) samples were mounted together on a ceramic heater and the temperature was monitored by a thermocouple attached at the top of the samples. NAP-XPS spectra were collected using selected photon energies, so that the obtained photoelectrons have the same kinetic energy (190 eV) and thus identical sample information depth (about 2 nm). Quantitative calculations were based on the peak areas, estimated after subtraction of a Shirley background and normalized by the photon flux and the photo-ionization cross-sections [16]. The samples were measured at a pressure of 3.5 mbar O_2 and ultra-high vacuum conditions (pressure *ca.* 5×10^{-8} mbar). The measurements were performed as follows: initially the two samples were subjected to an oxidation and reduction (redox) cycle in order to stabilize their surfaces. After the redox cycle both oxides were re-exposed to 3.5 mbar O_2 at 500 °C (± 5 °C) for 30 min and subsequently the temperature was lowered at 300 °C where NAP-XPS measurements were recorded. Consequently the chamber was evacuated down to 5×10^{-8} mbar while the sample temperature was increased at 500 °C. After 30 min at 500 °C the temperature was lowered down to 300 °C and XPS measurements were recorded at UHV environment. After the treatments, both samples were free of adventitious carbon as judged by the absence of C 1s signal.

3. Results and discussion

The NAP-XPS spectra of the Ni/YSZ sample in the two measurement environments are compared in figure 1. Please note that the spectra are normalized to the same intensity and are presented without any binding energy (BE) scale correction. In O_2 , the Ni $2p_{3/2}$ peak (fig. 1a) appears at 855.5 eV and is accompanied by an intense satellite around 862 eV. These features are clear evidences of the complete oxidation of nickel to NiO [12,17]. The O 1s peak (fig. 1b) is centered at 530.5 eV and can be assigned primarily to the convolution of lattice oxygen species from both NiO and YSZ [18]. The O 1s peak shows an apparent asymmetry at the high binding energy side which might be induced by adsorbed hydroxide species or defective sites within the oxide crystal [19]. The Zr $3d_{5/2}$ and Y $3d_{5/2}$ peaks at 182.3 and 157.1 eV respectively, are characteristic of zirconium and yttrium oxides in yttria-

stabilized zirconia [9,20]. Finally, the spectrum in the valence band region is dominated by the Ni 3d states of oxidized nickel at about 2 eV, which overlap with hybridized O 2p and Zr 4d states just above 3 eV [21]. Overall, from the NAP-XPS results it becomes evident that under the employed O₂ pressure conditions the surface of Ni/YSZ sample is fully oxidized to a mixture of NiO-ZrO₂-Y₂O₃.

Figure 1. NAP-XPS spectra of Ni/YSZ sample (a) Ni 2p_{3/2} ($h\nu=1050$ eV), (b) O 1s ($h\nu=725$ eV) (c) Zr 3d and valence band ($h\nu=275$ eV) and (d) Y 3d ($h\nu=350$ eV) recorded at 300 °C in O₂ (3.5 mbar) and UHV (5×10^{-8} mbar) conditions. Prior to spectra acquisition the electrode was annealed at 500 °C for 30 min at the same environment. The graph in yellow background compares the valence band and shows the valence band maximum (VBM) position. Both core level and valence band spectra are presented as received without any binding energy scale correction.

After O₂ treatment the NAP-XPS chamber was evacuated down to 5×10^{-8} mbar and the sample was then annealed at 500 °C for 30 min. Subsequently the temperature was lowered at 300 °C and XPS spectra were collected once again but in UHV this time. Comparison of the spectra peak shape recorded in UHV with that in O₂ does not show any apparent differences. However, all spectra, including the valence band maximum (VBM), are shifted of about 0.7 ± 0.1 eV in UHV as compared to O₂. Considering that apart from the energy shift, the peak shape remains identical in the two measurement conditions, it is rather unlikely that this modification is induced by changes in the Ni/YSZ valence state. Therefore, the relevant shift in UHV is not due to a chemical interaction

(chemical shift), but is related to changes at the energy level alignment between the sample and the spectrometer, as will be discussed in detail later in the text.

The NAP-XPS spectra of the LSCF electrode under identical conditions are presented in figure 2. In O₂ atmosphere the La 3d_{5/2} peak (fig. 2a) at 834.6 eV is accompanied by a strong satellite shifted by about 3.9 eV, which is characteristic for La³⁺ ions in perovskite structure [22]. The O 1s spectrum (fig. 2b) is similar with previous reports of LSF perovskite electrodes [23]. After peak deconvolution the O 1s peak reveals the presence of minimum two O 1s components. The dominant one at 530.7 eV has been related to the surface oxygen layer of the perovskite lattice [10], oxygen vacancies [24], lanthanum oxides [25] and Sr₂Co₂O₅ films [26]. Given the relatively small deviation in the reported binding energies it is not possible to distinguish between the above cases. However, the relatively large width of the peak at 530.7 eV (FWHM=1.79 eV) suggests that several oxygen species with similar BEs contribute to this O 1s component. The low-energy O 1s component at 529.4 eV (FWHM=1.35 eV) is typically assigned to oxygen from the perovskite lattice [10,24,26]. The Sr 3d spectrum can be deconvoluted into two doublets at 131.6 and 133.0 eV. Formation of two Sr 3d components with distinct depth distribution has been reported in several previous XPS studies of perovskite electrodes [26–29]. Typically, the low BE component (131.6 eV) is attributed to Sr species from the perovskite lattice, while the one at higher BEs (133 eV) to surface Sr oxide species (SrO_x) [26–29]. The Cr 2p_{3/2} peak (fig. 2c) appears at 576.2 eV, which is in good agreement with previous reports for the Cr³⁺ oxidation state [30]. Finally, the spectra of the valence band region shown in yellow background are due to hybridized states of the O 2p band and the metal cations of perovskite valence band [31]. Please note that due to the low amount of Fe-doping in the LSCF sample the signal of Fe 2p spectra was at the noise level and therefore they are not presented here. However, as judged from the absorption spectroscopy (not included here) the oxidation state of iron was not influenced by the UHV environment, similar to all the other elements of LSCF sample.

Comparison of the spectra recorded in O₂ and UHV shown in fig. 2 reveals a more complicated case for LSCF as compared to the Ni/YSZ sample. In particular the La 3d, Cr 3d and VB spectra have identical peak shape and binding energy in both UHV and O₂ environments. This reflects the good electronic conductivity of LSCF which compensates the loss of photoelectrons during XPS measurements [32]. However, close inspection of the Sr 3d peak in the two measurement conditions shows some subtle but critical differences. In particular, as clearly shown by the Sr 3d peak fitting procedure (figure 2c), the lattice Sr 3d peak is fixed at 131.6 eV, while the surface component shifts about 0.4 eV towards higher BEs in UHV as compared to O₂. A slightly smaller binding energy shift was also found for the O 1s component at 530.7 eV (fig. 2b). As will be discussed later, the

differences in the two conditions are induced by differences in the electronic conductivity of the distinct surface areas.

Figure 2. NAP-XPS spectra of LSCF sample (a) La 3d_{5/2} ($h\nu= 1030$ eV), (b) O 1s ($h\nu= 725$ eV) (c) Sr 3d and valence band ($h\nu= 325$ eV) (d) Cr 2p ($h\nu= 770$ eV) recorded at 300 °C in O₂ (3.5 mbar) and UHV (5×10^{-8} mbar) conditions. Prior to spectra acquisition the electrode was annealed at 500 °C for 30 min at the same environment. The graph in yellow background compares the valence band and shows the Fermi Level (E_{Fermi}) position. Both core level and valence band spectra are presented as received without binding energy scale correction.

Apart from the chemical state, the surface composition is another important characteristic which might be influenced by the sample environment. The calculated atomic concentration of the two samples under O₂ and UHV conditions are shown in Table 1. As is evident in the case of Ni/YSZ the surface composition does not change in UHV, while for LSCF there is a small increase of Sr in the expense of La. This in combination to the spectra analysis presented in fig. 1 and 2, suggests that UHV conditions do not induce any compositional modification on the surface of the pre-oxidized Ni/YSZ electrode. In the case of LSCF one can only refer to a limited surface segregation of Sr in UHV, which confirms previous studies reporting more Sr on the surface of electrodes exposed to low oxygen partial pressures [10].

Table 1. The atomic concentration at the outer 2 nm of the surface as calculated in the basis of NAP-XPS peak areas for Ni/YSZ and LSCF electrodes in the 3.5 mbar O₂ atmosphere as well as at the consequent measurements under UHV conditions.

		%Ni	%YSZ		%La	%Sr	%Cr	%Fe
O ₂	Ni/YSZ	80,8	19,2	LSCF	64,7	8,2	22,6	4,5
UHV		81,0	19,0		63,0	10,4	22,2	4,4

The observed differences at the binding energy shifts at the two measurements conditions found for the two samples can be rationalized by the energy diagrams shown in figure 3. As discussed above, in the case of the Ni/YSZ sample, the identical spectra shapes do not allow attributing the observed shifts to chemical shifts. The most plausible explanation for the energy scale shift of Ni/YSZ in UHV measurements is the building of electrostatic charging on the sample surface upon photoionization. This effect is typically observed in vacuum-based XPS for low- or non-conductive samples, like Ni/YSZ [21,33]. In this case the pinning of the Fermi levels between the sample and spectrometer does not occur and a positive charge builds up upon emission of photoelectrons and secondary electrons, which results to a shift of the photoemission lines. In the case of NAP-XPS measurements the incident photon beam irradiates the O₂ gas volume above the sample and generates additional electrons. As has been reported before [11,34] these low energy electrons compensate the charge at the sample surface and align the sample/spectrometer Fermi levels (E_{Fermi}), similar to an electron flood gun. As explained by the energy diagrams shown in fig. 3a and b, when the E_{Fermi} of the NiO-YSZ sample and the spectrometer cannot be aligned due to poor electron conductivity (this is the UHV case), a positive charge is built on the sample. This will decrease the measured photoelectron kinetic energy which will be reflected in an apparent increase of the BEs.

In the case of the LSCF sample the La, Fe, Cr related XPS peaks have identical position and shape in the two conditions, while those of Sr and O are modified. The peak fitting analysis shown in figure 2c suggests that these modifications are induced by a shift of the Sr 3d component related to surface strontium oxide species. Previously observed shifts of the Sr 3d peak BE have been attributed to the interaction of Sr cations with oxygen vacancies. In particular, J. Kuyyalil et al. reported that oxygen defects which are created by Ar⁺ ion sputtering on La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3- δ} (100) surfaces, interact with Sr ions and shift the Sr 3d towards lower BEs [24]. Therefore, if the observed Sr 3d shift in our case was induced by changes of the number of oxygen vacancies at the two measurement conditions, then LSCF should maintain a higher amount of oxygen vacancies in O₂ than in the consequent UHV environment according to the assignment of ref. [24]. However, this is very unlikely to happen since it is in contradiction with the reported lattice oxygen loss on perovskites upon annealing in low

oxygen pressures [35,36]. Consequently, the origin of the Sr 3d and O 1s modification is not a chemical shift induced by changes in the surface composition.

A more reasonable hypothesis to explain the observed shift of the surface, but not of the bulk Sr 3d component, is particular differences of the electrical contact between the two species and the analyser. It is known that strontium oxide (SrO_x) is a wide band gap insulator [37] and therefore an electrostatic charging is expected to build at the surface SrO_x layer in UHV, similar to the observations for Ni/YSZ. As shown in the energy diagram of figures 3c and d, the charge compensation for the good electronic conductor LSCF is effective since the sample is electrically connected to the ground and through this to the spectrometer. On the contrary, electrons cannot transfer through the insulating SrO_x surface layer. Accordingly, when the charge compensation through the gas phase is not possible (i.e. in UHV), electrostatic charge is built at this layer (see energy diagram in the figure 3d).

The model described above does not only rationalize our experimental data, but can also partly explain the broad BE distribution (ca. 3 eV) reported for surface Sr 3d species in the literature [26]. In the analysis of Sr 3d spectra from Sr-containing perovskites it is generally believed that the perovskite is in electrical contact with the spectrometer. We have shown however that this assumption might not be accurate and the energy level alignment is more complex involving both the Fermi levels of the conductive perovskite in the bulk, and that of the insulating SrO_x layer segregated on its surface. In UHV conditions charge compensation of the SrO_x mainly occurs by electron tunneling through the substrate and therefore the observed Sr 3d BE shift differs from case to case since it is influenced by several parameters, such as the thickness and the conductivity of the SrO_x film. We showed that comparison of UHV and NAP-XPS experiments can help to distinguish if the BE shift is due to a chemical effect or if it is caused by electrostatic charging due to poor electrical conductivity.

In addition to that, the comparison of UHV and NAP-XPS spectra can be a useful tool to acquire qualitative information about the electrical conductivity of specific surface sites. This has important implications when the perovskites are used as electrodes, for example in solid oxide fuel cell applications. We showed here that although the samples exhibit sufficient bulk conductivity as shown by the BEs, the areas which are covered by segregated SrO_x have significantly lower electronic conductivity. Therefore in applications that involve chemical processes (e.g. electrochemical reactions), where electrons should transfer from the surface of the electrode towards a current collector, surface conductivity is a crucial parameter of the electrode performance.

Figure 3. Schematic energy band diagrams showing the position of the core levels of the sample in relation to the Fermi energy level of the spectrometer: **a)** Ni/YSZ in O_2 , **b)** Ni/YSZ in UHV, **c)** LSCF in O_2 and **d)** LSCF in UHV.

4. Conclusions

Two complex oxides, typically used as electrodes in solid oxide electrochemical cells, were analyzed by XPS under 3.5 mbar of O_2 and subsequently in UHV conditions. We have shown that the surface state formed in O_2 remains to a large degree stable under UHV conditions. In addition, we demonstrated that shifts in the binding energy position of the photoemission peaks can be used to retrieve information about the electrical conductivity of the specific surface components. This observation can be used in future investigations in order to draw conclusions from XPS spectra about the electrical conductivity of complex electrode surfaces.

Acknowledgments

The research leading to these results has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under the project SElySOs with grant agreement No 671481. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and Greece, Germany, Czech Republic, France, Norway. Finally, we acknowledge synchrotron SOLEIL for the allocation of the beamtime and SOLEIL beamline scientists for the use of TEMPO beamline.

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